

The pmr spectrum of $[\text{Ph}_4\text{Sb}]_2[\text{NiCl}_4]$ in DMSO-d_6 showed complex multiplets in the range δ 7.47-7.90 which were attributed to the aromatic protons.

Attempts were made to synthesize the complexes of anhydrous metal chlorides with triphenylantimony dichloride. However, these reactions were unsuccessful probably because of the lower stability of C-Sb bond compared to C-P or C-As bond.

Triphenylstibine reduced copper(II) chloride to copper(I) chloride, when reacted in 1:2 molar ratio under dry nitrogen atmosphere and itself was converted into the corresponding dichloride. Similar reduction products have been reported by other workers^{15,16} also. However, when triphenylstibine was reacted with anhydrous zinc(II) chloride, a metathetic reaction occurred between the two, cleaving the C-Sb bond with the formation of Ph_3SbCl and PhZnCl . This can be represented as $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb} + \text{ZnCl}_2 \rightarrow \text{Ph}_2\text{SbCl} + \text{PhZnCl}$. The products, though not obtained in very pure state, were confirmed by elemental analyses and melting point data. Such a cleavage of C-Sb bond by mercury and some other metal compounds have also been reported earlier¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

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References

- H. K. SHARMA, S. N. DUBEY and D. M. PURI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, **20A**, 620.
- H. K. SHARMA, S. N. DUBEY and D. M. PURI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1981, **90**, 555.
- H. K. SHARMA, S. N. DUBEY and D. M. PURI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982, **21A**, 619.
- T. MOELLER, "Inorganic Syntheses", McGraw Hill Book Company, Inc., 1957, Vol. 5, p. 153.
- G. ONDREJORIC, D. MAKANOVA, D. VALIGURA and J. GAZO, *Z. Chem.*, 1973, **13**, 193; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, **79**, 137236g.
- J. CHATT and F. O. MANN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1192.
- R. L. MCKENNEY and H. H. SISLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1178.
- R. J. H. CLARK and T. M. DUNN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1198.
- D. M. ADAMS, J. CHATT, J. M. DAVIDSON and J. GERRATT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2189.
- A. SABATINI and L. SACCONI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 17.
- N. S. GILL and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3997.
- L. NALDINI and A. SACCO, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1959, **89**, 2258; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, **55**, 5390a.
- B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", (Eds.) J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINSON, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1967, p. 407.
- B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1966, p. 283.
- D. VALIGURA and J. GAZO, *Z. Chem.*, 1973, **13**, 193; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, **79**, 137236g.
- S. N. BHATTACHARYA and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **18A**, 515.

- M. S. MALINOVSKY and S. P. OLIFIRENKO, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1955, **25**, 122; *Chem. Abs.*, 1956, **50**, 1646c.
- A. E. BORISOV, *Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR, Otd. Khim. Nauk.*, 1951, 402; *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, **46**, 9706.
- M & T Chemicals, Inc., Neth., *Chem. Abs.*, 1966, **64**, 9766.

Studies on the Metal Chelates of 8-Hydroxy-quinolino-5-(*p*-Tolyl)sulphonamide as Potential Drugs

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THE chemistry of quinoline and *p*-toluene sulphonamides has attracted special attention because of their therapeutic properties^{1,2}. Some of the sulphonamides are used in the treatment of cancer³, tuberculosis⁴, diabetes⁵, malaria⁶, leprosy⁷ and convulsion⁸. They are also active against different types of bacteria. It has recently been observed that some drugs have increased activity when administered as metal complexes, 'more so as their metal chelates'^{9,10}. A similar mechanism was also observed in our previous study¹¹⁻¹³. In continuation of the previous work and to test the change in antibacterial activity of ligands on chelation, we report here the synthesis of metal chelates of 8-hydroxyquinolino-5-(*p*-tolyl)sulphonamide [HQTS] with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II) metals.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and recrystallized. The metal-ligand ratio was determined by conductometric titrations and Job's method of continuous variation. IR spectra were recorded on an automatic Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in KBr phase. Metals were estimated by standard methods¹⁴, sulphur by modified Messenger's method¹⁵ and nitrogen by modified Kjeldahl's method¹⁶.

The ligand HQTS was prepared by the general method¹² by taking 8-hydroxyquinoline as the starting material. The ligand was dissolved in warm distilled water. 0.1 M solution of the ligand was treated with 0.1 M aqueous solution of the metal salts at 50-60°. The pH was maintained between 8-9 by using borate buffer. The resulting precipitates of the chelates were digested on a water bath for 30 min, filtered, washed and recrystallized.

IR spectra : A broad distinct band at 2900 cm^{-1} was found in the spectrum of HQTS. This value is less than the prescribed limit (3700-3300 cm^{-1}) for -OH group and is due to hydrogen bonding^{17,18}. On this basis the intramolecular hydrogen bonded chelate structure (-O-H-N) was proposed for

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HQTS. A critical examination of the spectra of the metal chelates indicates that the band at 2900 cm^{-1} present in HQTS, shifts to higher values ($3500\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the chelates. Thus, the bands between $3500\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which appear in all chelates on metal chelate formation, are not present in the original ligand^{19,20}. The disappearance of H-bonded --OH in the ligand and its reappearance in the metal chelates are suggestive of O--M--N bond formation where M is a metal atom. The band of medium intensity at 1610 cm^{-1} in HQTS shifts to lower values with weak intensity in the spectra of chelates. It is due to $\text{M}\leftarrow\text{N}$ bond formation. The presence of sulphonamide group has been established by a characteristic band in the vicinity of the region 1370 cm^{-1} ^{21,22}.

Results and Discussion

The metal : ligand ratio as determined by conductometric titrations and Job's method of continuous variation was found to be 1 : 2. The ratio is further confirmed by elemental analyses. The colour, composition and the results of elemental analyses are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Compound	Composition*	Colour
1.	HQTS	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{SN}_2\text{O}_2$	White flakes
2.	Fe-HQTS	$\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{SN}_2\text{O}_2)_2$	Brown
3.	Co-HQTS	$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{SN}_2\text{O}_2)_2$	Blue
4.	Ni-HQTS	$\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{SN}_2\text{O}_2)_2$	Green
5.	Cu-HQTS	$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{SN}_2\text{O}_2)_2$	Blue
6.	Cd-HQTS	$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{SN}_2\text{O}_2)_2$	White
7.	Pb-HQTS	$\text{Pb}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{SN}_2\text{O}_2)_2$	Yellow

* All the compounds gave consistent elemental analysis for S, N and metal.

The reaction may be written as

The structure of the metal chelate is in good agreement with that reported in literature²³.

The m.p.s were determined by open capillary tubes, which were more than 300° and are uncorrected.

Screening for antibacterial activity: The bacteriostatic properties of the ligand and its metal chelates were studied by the usual cup-plate agar diffusion technique²⁴ against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. 1% (w/v) solutions of the chelates were prepared. Four holes (about 5 mm in diameter each) were cut in the agar medium inoculated with culture and 0.1 ml of 1% solution of the compounds was put in each hole. The dishes were allowed to remain in the

refrigerator at $4\text{--}8^\circ$ for about 0.5 hr to allow the diffusion of the solutions and were then incubated at $37\pm 1^\circ$ for 24 hr. The zones of inhibition were noted by measuring with the callipers. The control with solvent under identical conditions showed no activity. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Compound	Antibacterial activity (mm)	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	HQTS	—	—
2.	Fe-HQTS	18	20
3.	Co-HQTS	16	—
4.	Ni-HQTS	—	—
5.	Cu-HQTS	20	22
6.	Cd-HQTS	—	16
7.	Pb-HQTS	—	22

Compounds No. 1 and 4 showed no activity against both the organisms while compounds No. 6 and 7 showed activity against *E. coli* only. Compound No. 3 showed activity against *S. aureus* only. The remaining compounds were found active against both the organisms. It can thus be said that in general, the antibacterial activity of HQTS is enhanced on complexation with metals.

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References

- E. PROFFIT and G. BUCHMANN, *Arzneimittel Forsch.*, 1960, **10**, 181; *Chem. Abs.*, **53**, 2229i.
- H. NISHIHARA, *J. Biol. Chem. Japan*, 1953, **40**, 579.
- Hoffman la Roche & Co., *Swiss Patent*, 1957, 416648.
- J. A. VAICHULIS, *U. S. Patent*, 1966, 3 272 352.
- H. DIETRICH, *Swiss Patent*, 1968, 454874.
- L. H. SCHMIDT, *Ann. Rev. Microbiol.*, 1969, **23**, 427.
- G. TARBINI, *Proc. Int. Cong. Chemotherapy*, 1967, **2**, 909.
- S. AKTIESEI and F. KABET, *Dan. Patent*, 1968, 108626.
- D. R. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **72**, 203.
- A. FURST and R. T. HARO, *Progr. Exp. Tumor Res.*, 1969, **12**, 102.
- G. D. TIWARI and M. N. MISHRA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1980, **49**, 8.
- G. D. TIWARI and M. N. MISHRA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1981, **50**, 809.
- G. D. TIWARI and M. N. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 362.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. Ltd., London, 3rd Edn., 1962.
- G. D. TIWARI, G. S. JOHAR, U. AGARWALA and S. R. TRIVEDI, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **32**, 252.
- M. ASHRAF, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 555.
- J. B. HENDRICKSON, D. J. GRAM and G. S. HAMMOND, "Organic Chemistry", Mc. Graw Hill, Kogakusha Ltd., Tokyo, 3rd Edn., 1970, 260.
- G. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1968, 184.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, 1964, 105.
- K. VENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 1270.
- R. GROVER and B. G. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 578.
- G. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1968.
- T. NORTIA, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, **9**, 861.
- British Pharmacopoeia, Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1953, 796.